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Abstract:

This report summarises the achievements and work performed during the second year of MuCol, also in collaboration with the wider International Muon Collider Collaboration. A brief summary per work package (WP) is presented.

MuCol Consortium, 2025

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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1. INTRODUCTION

MuCol activities have progressed remarkably in the second year, since most of the positions foreseen by the project have been filled, including many “in-kind” contributions provided by the participating institutes. Therefore, there has been a significant progress from the technical and scientific point of view as described in chapter 3 of this report. The important change during 2024 is that the CERN Council decided to bring forward the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU) by one year to issue a recommendation for the future large project at CERN in a time frame that allows CERN to properly compete with the Chinese project CepC, which is supposed to receive a final approval in December 2025.

The MuCol Consortium achievements have been integrated into the contributions of the International Muon Collider Collaboration (IMCC) in the different reports that are currently being written for the 2026 update of the European strategy. The deadline for the submission of those inputs has been fixed to 31st March 2025, therefore the references to those documents are not yet available at the time of writing this report. A preliminary review of the IMCC R&D programme, including all the inputs of MuCol, its achievements and the proposals for the future, have been reviewed on 26 February 2025 by a panel of experts designated by the Laboratory’s Directors Group (LDG), which is a panel of directors of the main European laboratories that provide continuous advice to CERN Council about R&D priorities for CERN’s future. The MuCol Project Leader (D. Schulte) was invited to report on the achievements of MuCol and of the IMCC, and the LDG panel will soon report to the CERN Council providing recommendations for future funding of the R&D programme.

The present document gives a summary of the achievements of the second year of MuCol.

2. STATUS OF THE MUCOL CONSORTIUM

During the second year of the project, the MuCol Consortium focused on the understanding of the impact of the tentative parameters (MuCol Milestone n. 3) on the design of the different sections of the Muon Collider complex and on the design of the hardware. During the year several iterations were done, leading to the publication of an updated set of parameters (MuCol Milestone n. 5).

This second version of the list of parameters has been made possible by the various iterations on the accelerator designs (WP3, WP4, WP5) with physics (WP2) and the hardware studies (WP6, WP7, WP8). Several workshops have been organised to discuss either the specificities of a given work package, or to bring together expert of different fields to get to a common understanding of the parameters. The list of workshops is reported below:

- IMCC Demonstrator workshop (Fermilab, 30 Oct - 1 Nov 2024) [1]
- Early Career Researchers & Muon Colliders (Zoom, 28 Aug 2024) [2]
- IMCC Detector and MDI workshop (CERN, 25-26 Jun 2024) [3]
- MuCol Mini-Workshop on Rapid Cycled Synchrotrons, pulsed magnets and powering (CERN, 15 May 2024) [4]
- IMCC and MuCol Annual Meeting 2024 (CERN, 12-15 Mar 2024) [5]
- IMCC and MuCol MDI workshop 2024 (CERN, 11-12 Mar 2024) [6]

3. SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ACHIEVEMENTS AND OUTLOOK FOR THE NEXT PERIOD

In the following the main achievements for each work package (WP) are outlined. A more extensive description is included in an activity report that will be published in April 2025 by the IMCC. In the first paragraph we will report about the present status of the physics case studies for a Muon Collider at up to around 10 TeV. Although these kinds of studies are not part of MuCol, they provide a justification for the work done.

3.1. PHYSICS CASE FOR A 10 TEV MUON COLLIDER

A muon collider is a high energy electroweak collider, It can access directly and precisely the underlying simplicity of the Standard Model in its high-energy regime of “unbroken” electroweak symmetry, This makes it an ideal and unique machine to investigate fundamental questions about our universe – both long-held ones and more recent ones sparked by the LHC, Simultaneously, it is a paradigm-shifting tool for particle physics representing the first high-energy, high-precision compact collider, It combines the precision of a lepton collider with the energy reach of a hadron collider, yielding a physics potential significantly greater than the sum of its individual parts, This enables unparalleled exploration of the Electroweak-Higgs Unification era that we have entered since the discovery of the Higgs, We can now hope to answer the question of why electroweak symmetry breaking (EWSB) occurs by directly probing the transition between the “broken” and “unbroken” symmetry regimes, Furthermore, we can address the phase diagram of EWSB and quantitatively investigate the earliest moments in our universe and its ultimate fate, With high energy EW collisions we can also search for physics beyond the SM directly using a muon collider as an unrivaled EW discovery machine, These same high energy high precision collisions allow us also to probe new physics to scales far beyond the collider’s energy and study the Standard Model (SM) in new domains where new phenomena emerge,

For example, a muon collider can make exquisite measurements of TeV-scale vector boson scattering, This is due to the inherently quantum and relativistic effect of abundant effective vector bosons contained in a high energy muon, which gives rise to large collision rates with low backgrounds, Such measurements enable the first precision experimental tests of the “unitarization” of massive gauge boson scattering, arguably the foremost prediction of Electroweak symmetry breaking, High-energy, high-precision studies of the Higgs and vector bosons also give the first detailed probes of the “Electroweak symmetry restoration” realm within the SM, The high-energy nature of the muon collider also enables new insights into, and tests of, the “quantum compositeness” of particles, This is ideally studied in Electroweak processes due to their perturbative and thus in principle calculable nature (unlike the strong interactions), and the physical mass gap that makes “particles” fully well defined as asymptotic states unlike in QED. Finally, the intrinsic nature of a high-energy muon collider provides the most abundant and best characterized source of high energy neutrino-target collisions conceived thus far. The neutrino physics program at a muon collider provides a high-energy complement to current and future long-baseline neutrino experiments.

Fig. 1: Muon collider theory papers over time (left) core directions of physics case (right)

A muon collider simultaneously offers numerous pathways to search for BSM physics by utilising the energy reach, precision measurement capabilities, and the combination thereof. This has led to an enormous amount of theoretical activity since the last strategy process building on these possibilities, as demonstrated in Fig. 1. The same abundant vector boson scattering that enables exploration of new SM phenomena also furnishes a next-generation Higgs factory. In certain channels this allows an order of magnitude or more improvement in the understanding of Higgs properties, including its potential. This allows one to experimentally probe BSM contributions that could change the nature of the EW phase transition and baryogenesis, the ultimate fate of our vacuum and the “Higgs portal” to hidden sectors. Furthermore the energy reach of a muon collider allows one to test the origin of any deviation from SM properties found in a precision measurement at the same collider, and by extension any previous Higgs Factory. The combination of precision and energy also allows one to probe BSM possibilities such as “Higgs compositeness” up to the $O(100)$ TeV scale, far beyond the reach of any other proposed collider. Reaching the 10 TeV scale directly also enables unmatched probes of new EW particles such as those responsible for the simplest dark matter paradigms, or alternatively probing the possibility of new gauge forces in many cases to unrivaled scales. The combination of energy and precision also revolutionises flavor physics by enabling direct tests of fermions interactions, with a new physics scale reach that is comparable or superior to the one attainable by traditional studies of meson or leptons decays. This includes neutral current flavor tests sensitive to mediators at the 100 TeV scale, while also enabling new windows into SM flavor in the Higgs sector and potential explanations of neutrino masses with HNL searches.

The impressive physics potential of a muon collider is enabled by both its energy reach as well as its high luminosity. The luminosity goals of 10 TeV with $10/\text{ab}$ are naturally consistent with the emittance targets from cooling and the inherent increase of luminosity power efficiency at high energy. Furthermore, a muon collider is an innately stageable project in both luminosity and energy given a common front end for muon production and cooling. With a staged approach, considerable technical and financial risk could be retired and physics progress can be achieved along the path to the highest energies. Low energy stages could provide direct measurements of the Higgs width or experimentally and theoretically precise measurements of the top mass. Such low-energy muon colliders could be also considered as an independent satellite project at the muon collider complex. A 3 or 3.2 TeV stage can offer the first significant step beyond the HL-LHC in understanding the Higgs potential as well as testing certain DM candidates. A 7.6 TeV stage at CERN would extend our

understanding of EWSB even further allowing a differential test of EW restoration, especially relevant if luminosity goals are relaxed in the pursuit of the highest energies, Furthermore, while 10 TeV is the ultimate goal of this study, it is not the final goal of particle colliders nor the highest conceivable energy of a muon collider in the far future,

Successfully building a muon collider allows us to reset the collider landscape with this paradigm shifting tool, Muon collider investment now lays the groundwork for coming generations to explore nature *directly* at even shorter distances, in likely the only sustainable and technically practical way for the future of HEP.

3.2. WP1: COORDINATION AND COMMUNICATION

MuCol is running now at cruise speed, with regular meetings organised by each WP according to tasks distribution and needs, and executive meetings of the work package leaders organised every month, although contacts among the coordinators and the WP leaders happen also outside the monthly meeting. The progress on the different subjects has been relevant under many aspects, which has been recognised by the panel of experts at the end of February 2025. Their report will become public in the next months.

All milestones and deliverables have been submitted on time, except this report where we asked a delay of one month to take into account eventual recommendations from the expert panel of the LDG.

About 50 publications have been submitted for review at the editorial board and have been published on different journals, conferences proceedings and internal notes or ArXiv as listed in Annex 1. The official reports of MuCol have been published on Zenodo [7]. All the scientific papers not linked with MuCol Milestones and Deliverables have been published on usual tools of the high energy physics and accelerator physics community (namely cds.cern.ch, arxiv.org and journals).

In 2024, the role of MuCol Gender Advisor focused on strengthening gender equity initiatives within the MuCol Consortium through awareness-building, possible mentorship program, and policy discussions. Efforts included facilitating discussions on implicit bias and gender representation, conducting one-on-one conversations with female physicists to understand their experiences, and contributing to the development of an inclusive collaborative framework for MuCol and support early-career researchers. Engagement with CERN's Diversity & Inclusion Office helped align MuCol's gender equity goals with broader institutional and EU frameworks, while advocacy for greater female representation in leadership aimed to create more inclusive governance. To measure impact, storytelling sessions were held where female physicists shared their career journeys, challenges, and aspirations, complemented by an anonymous survey at the March 2024 MuCol annual meeting, which highlighted increased awareness of gender equity. Moving forward, the focus remains on institutionalizing these efforts, ensuring gender-equity considerations are embedded in policy discussions, and mentorship programs to foster a more inclusive and supportive research environment within MuCol.

Finally, in view of the anticipation of the ESPPU to 2025, WP1 accelerated on the possible siting at CERN of a muon collider (while the parameters of the two Milestones 3 and 5 relate to a green field implementation). A very convenient placement has been found, that makes use of the already existing tunnels hosting presently the CERN SPS, and the LHC, reducing the civil engineering works to a few km of tunnels (around 20 km), shown in Fig. 2. All the complex stays on land already attributed to CERN by the two host states Switzerland and France. Particular attention has been put on the aspects of the emergence of neutrino radiation on surface, where at the moment we do not see

any problem, with the exception of the cones of neutrinos originating in the interaction regions from muon decays. In one direction radiation will come out in the middle of the Mediterranean Sea, therefore not pointing to any inhabited area, and on the other side on a steep portion of the Jura mountains, where no human settlement is possible. The implications both from the legal point of view and from the public perception have yet to be studied. The levels of radiation are not expected to exceed legal values by a significant amount, but detailed studies will be performed during the remainder of the study period.

Fig. 2: Placement on the CERN site of a Muon Collider complex. After a proton linac, the beam is transported through the existing CERN-SPS to a target area on the Preveessin site, going through cooling and pre-acceleration section then RCS 1 and 2 in the CERN-SPS and RCS 3-4 in the LHC tunnel, and finally a new 10 km tunnel for the collider in red.

3.3. WP2: PHYSICS AND DETECTOR REQUIREMENTS

In this second year more detailed studies of the 3 TeV detector performances have been performed. The background effects at $\sqrt{s}=3$ TeV have been studied using the interaction region (IR) designed by MAP [8], which includes the shielding structure (nozzle). The impact of beam-induced background (BIB) on the detector has been discussed extensively in various meetings and published in several papers with the most recent in [9]. The detector design was adapted to this unique environment, and reconstruction algorithms were developed to mitigate the effects of the irreducible component of the

beam-induced background. The results have been presented at conferences and summarized in a publication [10].

Fig. 3: The MAIA Detector Concept

Muon collisions at 10 TeV center-of-mass energy are being studied in this project for the first time. The design of the IR has been frozen to produce initial results for the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU). The nozzle configuration, that initially considered a geometry inspired by the work of MAP, was updated to simulate the beam-induced background. The characteristic of such background at $\sqrt{s}=10$ TeV have been discussed in the biweekly Physics & Detector meetings and presented at the conference [11].

Fig. 4: the MUSIC Detector Concept

Two detector design concepts have been developed, MAIA and MUSIC [12] to optimize 10 TeV center-of-mass muon collisions collection and study them.

Both designs share a similar structure, a cylindrical shape 11.4 m in length with a diameter of 12.8 m. The main detector components are a tracking system, an electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL), a hadronic calorimeter (HCAL) and a muon system.

A superconducting solenoid is also envisioned to provide bending power for the measurement of charged particle momenta within the tracking system. While the tracking system has a similar structure, the MAIA detector has the solenoid just outside the tracking system and before the ECAL, while MUSIC places the solenoid magnet between ECAL and HCAL.

The determination of performance and physics benchmarks is currently underway, with and they will be published as contributions to the ESPPU. Preliminary results have been presented to a conference [12].

The sub-detectors most affected by the machine-induced background are the tracker and the electromagnetic calorimeter in the case of MUSIC detector. Fig. 6 (left) shows the average occupancy, expressed as the of number of hits per cm^2 , as a function of the tracker system layer due to machine-induced background. To mitigate the impact of this high hit density on track reconstruction, a dedicated tracking algorithm has been developed. Fig. 6 (right) reports the occupancy of the ECAL and HCAL endcap sections, as a function of the longitudinal distance from the interaction point, where it is evident the large amount of energy in the inner layers of ECAL.

Fig. 6: (left): average occupancy, expressed as the of number of hits per cm^2 , as a function of the tracker system layer due to machine-induced background; (right) the occupancy of the ECAL and HCAL endcap sections, as a function of the longitudinal distance from the interaction point

The reports submitted to the ESPPU illustrate the performance on almost all the physics objects: tracks, photons, electrons and jets. These results were objectives of the WP due by the end of next year but they have been advanced to contribute to the anticipated timeline of the ESPP update.

3.4. WP3: PROTON COMPLEX

During the second year WP3 has been asked to perform the design not only for a 2MW at 5 GeV beam on target, but also to look into the possibility to produce a beam at 4 MW in order to have a back-up solution ready if the transmission of the muon bunches along the cooling and acceleration

sections would become insufficient to get to the required luminosity. For this reason, an increase of the beam energy to 10 GeV has been envisaged and preliminary simulations have been done.

The design is an evolution of the approaches followed by the HP-SPL [13], and the ESS [14] linacs. The present table of parameters, included in the “preliminary” set of parameters is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Summary of main parameters for the proton complex for two power options.

Parameter	Unit	Variant 1	Variant 2
Final Beam Power	MW	2	4
Linac Final energy	GeV	5	10
Repetition rate	Hz	5	
Protons on target	$\times 10^{14}$	5.0	
Accumulated bunch length	ns	120	
Initial rms energy spread	%	0.025	
Final rms bunch length	ns	2	
Final rms energy spread	%	1.5	0.6

A study of the effect of H^- stripping on the loss budget of such a machine was completed. The conclusions of this study are that the main component for the H^- stripping losses come from blackbody radiation stripping, which could be circumvented by cooling the vacuum chamber in warm areas and transfer lines below 200 K. Alternatively, the use of a coating that reduces secondary emission can be instigated. This applies to both variants. The normalised losses due to stripping as well as the power loss per length as a function of the temperature of the vacuum chamber can be seen in Fig. 7. The intra-beam scattering component is well under control even at higher energies as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: H stripping power loss from Blackbody radiation and a function of the vacuum chamber temperature.

Fig. 8: Intra-beam scattering stripping for a 10 GeV linac. Position zero is the start of the superconducting linac.

A baseline lattice for the accumulator and compressor for the 5 and 10 GeV variants, based on the studies for the neutrino factory at CERN [15] was revised and ported to Xsuite [16]. A series of simulations to verify the lattice behaviour over many turns was launched and indicated no major showstoppers for either variant when the beam is accumulated for over about 6000 turns, which corresponds to a linac working at a 5 Hz repetition rate. In the present version of accumulator ring no RF systems are implemented to achieve the desired performance, however, there will be a need for RF barrier buckets to avoid smearing on the bunches over the many turns of accumulation. Currently, the accumulator lengths and number of bunches envisioned for each energy dictate a possible chopping scheme needed for the linac. For the 5 GeV case, the parameters needed, 80 mA and 2.5 ms long pulse, are not too far from what can be achieved today however for the 4 MW case either some R&D is needed or the use of 2 sources in parallel could be an option in order to achieve a 5 ms H pulse from the source.

The compressor accepts bunches from the accumulator and performs a 90° bunch rotation in longitudinal phase space. A detailed study of the rotation for both power options was launched and optimization of the bunch length in order to achieve the 2 ns final bunch length, assuming an initial

rms momentum spread of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$, was established. For the 5 GeV, a space-charge driven lattice resonance is excited at the end of rotation causing emittance blow up and needing further study. Fig. 9 shows the initial and final 6D phase space of the bunches before and after compression for the 5 GeV case. For the 10 GeV case the rotation of the bunches is clean and no issues were encountered to reach the 2 ns bunch length so far.

Fig. 9: Example of bunch rotation for the 5 GeV case. (left) initial beam in blue and rotated beam in orange. (right) final bunch length at extraction.

A first look at the transport between ring and target of a 2 ns high current bunch has started. The bunches from the compressor for both energies (and powers) could be transported through a FODO lattice and focused to the specified beam sizes on the target surface without loss of quality and within the specification communicated by WP4 (target).

A detailed R&D plan list for the next 5 to 10 years with key issues for the Proton Complex has been established and will be submitted to the ESPPU process.

3.4.1. Collective effects for the proton driver (WP5)

Collective effects for the proton driver are described in this paragraph for convenience but have been studied in WP5.

In the proton driver, the single bunch intensity will reach $5.0 \cdot 10^{14}$ protons per bunch, with an emittance $\sim 9 \mu\text{m}$ and an energy of 5 GeV or 10 GeV. This intensity and energy regime makes the bunches more prone to coherent instabilities from space charge effects, in particular in the accumulator and compressor rings. The interplay with beam-coupling impedance effects is also important for the circular machines and it has been a topic investigated for more than two decades. Since few years quite some progress has been made in the understanding of this intricate mechanism but there are still some open points which need to be clarified.

In this framework, a general comparison of simulation codes for direct space charge simulation has been carried out. They use different analytical approaches to estimate the coherent mode frequency shifts as a function of bunch intensity. The codes BimBim, based on the Circulant Matrix Model (CMM); the Effective impedance method for space charge; GALACTIC based on the Vlasov equation; the boxcar model for space charge only; and the ABS model which assumes an Air-Bag bunch distribution in a Square well were compared. This comparison identified significant differences between models, and will help choose the correct model, understanding its limitations, for the space charge mode frequency shifts estimation in proton driver.

3.5. WP4: MUON PRODUCTION & COOLING

WP4 made significant progress during the second year in the optimisation of the performances of the cooling sections, and in the understanding of the constraints coming from the design of the associated hardware in collaboration with WP6, WP7 and WP8.

Fig. 10: Layout of the muon production and cooling sections.

The muon production and cooling system comprises several subsystems, as shown in Fig. 10. The protons provided by the proton complex intersect a target to produce pions. The target is immersed in a 20 T solenoid field, yielding a high pion flux. The field is rapidly tapered to 1.5 T. Pions and muons traverse a solenoid-focused chicane where high momentum beam impurities are removed followed by a Beryllium absorber which ranges out remnant low energy protons. The remaining beam passes through a longitudinal drift where any remaining pions decay. The beam is then captured longitudinally. A multi-frequency RF system that captures the beam into 21 bunches is required owing to the initially large longitudinal beam emittance. Another solenoid chicane system splits the beam by charge species, in preparation for the ionisation cooling system.

The ionisation cooling system comprises a series of solenoids, which focus the beam onto energy absorbers where the beam momentum is removed. The momentum is restored longitudinally using RF cavities resulting in a reduction in the beam's emittance (volume in position-momentum space). An initial rectilinear cooling system, Rectilinear A, reduces the beam emittance sufficiently that the many initial bunches can be merged into one single bunch. The beam is then cooled further to the final emittance, using a continuation of the rectilinear cooling system, Rectilinear B, followed by a sequence of high field solenoids operated ultimately with a low momentum (non-relativistic) beam. The beam is finally re-accelerated to semi-relativistic speeds so that it can be delivered to the acceleration system.

The key components in the Muon Production system, as designed by MAP [17], have been identified and the design has been optimised by the MuCol and IMCC teams. A significant improvement in performance has been achieved. The overall performance estimate of the ionisation cooling system is summarised in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: performance of the ionisation cooling system

The progress on the different sections that have been studied are detailed in the following sections.

3.5.1. Target and Capture section

The target team has designed a baseline radial build for the pion production target, taking into account radiation flux into the surrounding solenoid, heat load on the graphite target itself and appropriate cooling systems for the target and shielding. The radial build is detailed in Table 2. A 3D FLUKA model for the target area has been constructed and the pion and muon yield through the target system has been assessed. The FLUKA geometry implementation of the target area is shown in Fig. 12. The model is simplified with respect to Table 2. The yield results from simulations are presented in

Table 3, assuming a transverse beam sigma of 5 mm, a target rod radius of 15 mm and that all the muon and pions going in the chicane can be captured if their momentum is below 500 MeV/c. The magnet team have identified HTS technology as having greater tolerance to radiation issues. The target team have updated the design with reduced shielding and structural elements included.

Table 2: Dimensions used for the radial build of the target surrounded by a 20T solenoid.

Component	Material	r_i [mm]	r_e [mm]	Δr [mm]
Solenoid coils	HTS	700	-	-
Insulation	Insulation	690	700	10
Vacuum	Vacuum	670	690	20
Thermal shield	Copper & Water	651	670	19
Vacuum	Vacuum	631	651	20
Inner supporting tube	Stainless-steel	619	631	12
Vacuum	Vacuum	609	619	10
Outer Target shielding	Tungsten	599	609	10
Neutron absorber	Boron Carbide	594	599	5
Target shielding and neutron moderator	Stainless-steel	589	594	5
	Water	569	589	20
	Stainless-steel	564	569	5
	Tungsten	179	564	385
	Stainless-steel	174	179	5
Vacuum	Vacuum	173	174	1
Target vessel	Titanium	168	173	5
	Helium	155	168	13
	Titanium	150	155	5
	Helium	15	150	135
Target	Graphite	0	15	15

Table 3: Yield per unit energy proton beam [$10^{-2}/\text{GeV}/p^+$].

Yield [$10^{-2}/\text{GeV}/p^+$]	Proton beam energy [GeV]							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
μ^+	2.8	2.6	2.4	2.3	2.2	2.1	1.9	1.9
μ^-	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7
π^+	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.1	1	0.98	0.92	0.9
π^-	0.84	0.81	0.84	0.82	0.83	0.8	0.8	0.81

Preliminary concepts for the spent proton beam handling have been studied. It is challenging to extract the beam in the high field region and taper owing to the need to maintain a smooth field in this region and so extraction is foreseen in the chicane where fields are relatively lower. The pion and muon beam is deflected here by the solenoid field. The proton beam is much more rigid and so is relatively undeflected. A transition from a high radius solenoid to a low radius solenoid is envisioned to allow space for the protons to leave the beam pipe. It was found that the spent protons are not focused enough to avoid extreme radiation load to the chicane structure. At the same time, increasing the aperture size would require unprecedented currents in normal conducting magnets, whose radiation hardness is far superior over superconducting coils. Studies continue to explore the relative size of the solenoids, magnetic field shape and surrounding shielding to extract the beam at this point. Potential alternative solutions to be investigated are shortening the tapering region and changing the target material.

Fig. 12: Geometrical model of the target area implemented for FLUKA simulations depicted in XZ plane (top) and XY plane (bottom). The red dashed line indicates the Z position of the XY cross section picture.

Following the chicane and proton absorber, the beam is contained transversely by solenoid fields and drifts longitudinally. Slower particles arrive later at the downstream RF cavities. Weakly excited cavities provide a small amount of bunching, followed by gradually more strongly excited cavities, in order to capture the beam adiabatically into RF buckets. Because the beam is not captured, the RF frequency must be lower at downstream cavities to accommodate the late arrival of slower particles. Following capture the lower energy, late particles are accelerated. This is achieved by adjusting cavity frequency so that the late particles undergo an accelerating phase while the early particles undergo a bunching phase. Preliminary work has started to examine the dependence of RF frequency and transverse aperture in this system in order to provide an integrated optimisation with the early stages of the rectilinear cooling system.

3.5.2. Rectilinear Cooling system

The design of the rectilinear cooling lattice, based on the MAP design [17], is composed of two rectilinear cooling channels, one before (Rectilinear A) and one after (Rectilinear B) the bunch merging system. The lattice has been updated with respect to the original MAP design and yields an

improved performance of about a factor two. While here we briefly describe the lattice design and performance, the detailed study can be found in [18].

The rectilinear cooling system has a periodic lattice composed of a series of solenoid magnets which have a weak dipole field superimposed to enable emittance exchange. While the previous design used tilted solenoids to generate the dipole field, the updated MuCol design employs separate dipole magnets. This design choice facilitates the independent tuning of the dipole field. Each periodic unit, referred to as cooling cell, consists of solenoids with opposite polarity for tight focusing at the absorber, dipole magnets for dispersion generation, RF cavities for beam energy loss compensation and liquid hydrogen (LH₂) wedge absorbers.

Fig. 13: Schematic of the (left) A-type and (right) B-type cooling cell layout.

Two types of cooling cells are used in the present design: A-type and B-type cells, used for the pre-merge and post-merge sections, respectively. The conceptual layout of the two types of cooling cells is shown in Fig. 13. The primary difference between the two types of cells lies in the cell tune (number of betatron oscillations per cell). A-type cells operate with a cell tune below 1, which allows the lattice to accept a beam with a higher beam emittance, suitable for initial cooling. The A-type cell has a further advantage that the transverse betatron function at the center of the cell is equal to that at the start and end of the cell, which enables the use of an additional wedge absorber in the middle of the cell. B-type cells operate with a cell tune between 1 and 2, in a tighter focusing regime that enables cooling to lower emittances. As a result, these cells do not accept high-emittance beams and have a smaller momentum acceptance.

The RF cavities are modelled as perfect cylindrical pillbox cavities with thin Beryllium (Be) windows operating in the TM₀₁₀ mode. The Be windows electromagnetically seal the cavities, ensuring that the TM₀₁₀ mode is an appropriate model of the real field, and have been shown to increase the operational RF gradient in multi-Tesla magnetic fields [19]. Multiple independently phased RF cavities are used in each cell.

Rectilinear A and Rectilinear B lattices are composed of 4 A-type and 10 B-type stages, respectively. Each stage is a series of identical cooling cells, and the design of the cooling cell becomes more challenging (higher fields, more compact assembly, etc.) with increasing stage number. The hardware parameters for the whole rectilinear cooling system are listed in

Table 4: Main parameters for the rectilinear cooling cell components, including the cell geometry, solenoid fields, dipole fields, beam optics and wedge absorber geometry. Liquid hydrogen is used as the wedge absorber material for all stages. and Table 4.

Table 4: Main parameters for the rectilinear cooling cell components, including the cell geometry, solenoid fields, dipole fields, beam optics and wedge absorber geometry. Liquid hydrogen is used as the wedge absorber material for all stages.

	Cell Length (m)	Stage Length (m)	Pipe Radius (cm)	Max. Bz On-Axis (T)	Int. By (Tm)	β_{\perp}	Dx (mm)	On-Axis Wedge Len. (cm)	Wedge Angle (deg)
A-Stage 1	1.8	104.4	28	2.5	0.102	70	-60	14.5	45
A-Stage 2	1.2	106.8	16	3.7	0.147	45	-57	10.5	60
A-Stage 3	0.8	64.8	10	5.7	0.154	30	-40	15	100
A-Stage 4	0.7	86.8	8	7.2	0.186	23	-30	6.5	70
B-Stage 1	2.3	50.6	23	3.1	0.106	35	-51.8	37	110
B-Stage 2	1.8	66.6	19	3.9	0.138	30	-52.4	28	120
B-Stage 3	1.4	84.0	12.5	5.1	0.144	20	-40.6	24	115
B-Stage 4	1.2	66.0	9.5	6.6	0.163	15	-35.1	20	110
B-Stage 5	0.8	44.0	6	9.1	0.116	10	-17.7	12.5	120
B-Stage 6	0.7	38.5	4.5	11.5	0.087	6	-10.6	11	130
B-Stage 7	0.7	28.0	3.75	13	0.088	5	-9.8	10	130
B-Stage 8	0.65	46.15	2.85	15.8	0.073	3.8	-7	7	140
B-Stage 9	0.65	33.8	2.3	16.6	0.069	3	-6.1	7.5	140
B-Stage 10	0.63	29.61	2.0	17.2	0.069	2.7	-5.7	6.8	140

The performance of the rectilinear cooling system is shown in Table 5, in terms of the beam emittance and transmission at the end of each stage. The Rectilinear A section reduces the normalised transverse and longitudinal emittances from 16.96mm and 45.53mm to 1.24mm and 1.74mm, respectively, with an overall transmission rate of 49.6% including the muon decays. The Rectilinear B section reduces the normalised transverse and longitudinal emittances from 5.13mm and 9.99mm to 0.14mm and 1.56mm, respectively, with an overall transmission rate of 28.5% including the muon decays. The final transverse emittance achieved with this design is a factor of two smaller than in the US-MAP [17] design. This improvement is expected to significantly benefit the design of the final cooling section, which aims to achieve a normalised transverse emittance of $25\mu\text{m}$. The scenario of using coupled RF cavities has also been investigated. In this case, adjacent cavities operate with a π phase difference, and only one power coupler and feed through is required for a group of coupled RF cavities. The impact of using π -mode RF was studied on a cooling lattice comprised of 'B-Stage 5'-like cells. Comparisons with an identical cooling channel using normal mode RF reveal no significant differences in cooling performance. More details on this work, including a sensitivity analysis can be found in [18].

Table 4: Rectilinear cooling cell RF parameters.

	RF Frequency (MHz)	Num. RF	RF Length (cm)	Max. RF Gradient (MV/m)	RF Phase (deg)
A-Stage 1	352	6	19	27.4	18.5
A-Stage 2	352	4	19	26.4	23.2
A-Stage 3	704	5	9.5	31.5	23.7
A-Stage 4	704	4	9.5	31.7	25.7
B-Stage 1	352	6	25	21.2	29.9
B-Stage 2	352	5	22	21.7	27.2
B-Stage 3	352	4	19	24.9	29.8
B-Stage 4	352	3	22	24.3	31.3
B-Stage 5	704	5	9.5	22.5	24.3
B-Stage 6	704	4	9.5	28.2	22.1
B-Stage 7	704	4	9.5	28.5	18.4
B-Stage 8	704	4	9.5	27.1	14.5
B-Stage 9	704	4	9.5	29.7	11.9
B-Stage 10	704	4	9.5	24.9	12.2

Table 5: Simulated performance of the rectilinear cooling lattice in terms of emittance reduction (transverse, longitudinal and 6D) and transmission, both per stage and cumulative.

	ϵ_T (mm)	ϵ_L (mm)	ϵ_{6D} (mm ³)	Stage Transmission (%)	Cumulative Transmission (%)
Start	16.96	45.53	13500		100
A-Stage 1	5.17	18.31	492.60	75.2	75.2
A-Stage 2	2.47	7.11	44.03	84.4	63.5
A-Stage 3	1.56	3.88	9.59	85.6	54.3
A-Stage 4	1.24	1.74	2.86	91.3	49.6
Bunch merge	5.13	9.99	262.5	78.0	38.7
B-Stage 1	2.89	9.09	76.07	85.2	33.0
B-Stage 2	1.99	6.58	26.68	89.4	29.4
B-Stage 3	1.27	4.05	6.73	87.5	25.8
B-Stage 4	0.93	3.16	2.83	89.8	23.2

B-Stage 5	0.70	2.51	1.32	89.4	20.7
B-Stage 6	0.48	2.29	0.55	88.4	18.2
B-Stage 7	0.39	2.06	0.31	92.8	17.0
B-Stage 8	0.26	1.86	0.13	87.9	14.9
B-Stage 9	0.19	1.72	0.06	85.2	12.7
B-Stage 10	0.14	1.56	0.03	87.1	11.1

After undergoing sufficient cooling in the Rectilinear A section, the initial train of bunches are merged into a single bunch by the bunch merging system. The most up-to-date design of the bunch merging scheme has been carried out by MAP and is described in detail in [20]. In this scheme, 21 bunches are merged in the longitudinal phase space into seven bunches, which then follow seven paths of different lengths and reach a collecting funnel at the same time to be merged transversely.

3.5.3. Final Cooling

Final cooling is necessary to provide further reduction of the transverse emittance, while allowing reasonable increases in the longitudinal emittance. The design and performance of the final cooling is a key indicator for the muon collider as it defines the minimum emittance for all downstream systems, including acceleration and collider, which has a direct impact on the available luminosity. In addition, the final cooling is a hot spot for losses, both from decays - as it has the lowest muon energy across the whole complex - and from losses within the absorber, perpetuated by particles outside the dynamic aperture from strong non-linear effects. This means a lattice which maximises final cooling transmission has a significant impact on the downstream intensity of the beam, and could even relax beam power requirements upstream, at the target.

The final cooling design is similar to that of the rectilinear cooling, but without the use of dipoles and wedge absorbers. In addition, the lattice designs are shorter, with approximately 10 cells over 100m of beamline. This reduces the periodicity condition of the system compared to the rectilinear cooling. To maximize focusing of the beam throughout the absorbers, large solenoid fields are used.

The performance of the final cooling lattice is heavily dependent on the initial conditions obtained from the rectilinear cooling channel. The baseline design is that the rectilinear cooling obtains $\varepsilon_T = 300\mu\text{m}$, and $\varepsilon_L = 1.5\mu\text{m}$. A lattice simulation exists for the baseline conditions, which is roughly equivalent to the end of B - Stage 8, therefore is referred to as "FC-RB8" for "Final Cooling from Rectilinear B-Stage 8". Given that a longer rectilinear lattice can provide additional 6D cooling, it can result in a shorter final cooling lattice, and therefore reduces longitudinal emittance increase, this lattice design is referred to as "FC-RB10" for "Final Cooling from Rectilinear B-Stage 10". FC-RB8 is simulated in RF-Track [21], and RC-RB10 is simulated in G4Beamline. Thorough benchmarks between the two codes have been performed. The summary table for both designs is shown in Table 6. The decision between the two lattice designs is conditional on the cost optimisation for an improvement of $\varepsilon_L = 82\text{mm} - 35\text{mm}$. For further details on the absorber lengths and RF cavity parameters, please refer to the 2024 Preliminary Parameter Report [22].

Fig. 14: Final cooling lattice diagram from Rectilinear Stage B8

A lattice schematic of FC-RB8 is shown in Fig. 14, which shows the magnetic fields (black line), relative to the position of the absorbers (grey boxes), with the gradient of the RF cavities represented by the heights of the blue and red boxes. The decreasing frequency of each RF cavity is written in red. The final few cells are modelled as liquid hydrogen, but in reality will be composed of gaseous hydrogen, hence the shorter absorber lengths.

Table 6: Final cooling lattice performance for two initial starting conditions, from Rectilinear Stage B8 and from Rectilinear Stage B10

3.5.4. Collective effects in the muon cooling

A first theoretical assessment of the magnitude of collective effects in the muon cooling has been performed. Three main effects have already been identified. The first two are linked to variations of the longitudinal focusing fields and are caused by space charge and beam loading in the rectilinear cooling. Indeed, the high bunch intensity (starting with $1 \cdot 10^{14}$ muons per bunch), combined with the high RF frequencies (in the 325MHz to 1056MHz range) generate a high-amplitude beam-induced voltage.

The rectilinear cooling lattice and the cavities design might require specific adaptation to mitigate these effects, in particular to maintain the required linear part of the fields. Limitations may then arise from the non-linearity of the collective fields, potentially increasing the tune spread. Pessimistic estimates are shown in Fig. 15.

Table 7: Final cooling lattice performance for two initial starting conditions, from Rectilinear Stage B8 and from Rectilinear Stage B10

Cell	ϵ_T (μm)	ϵ_L (mm)	N_T (%)	$E_{\text{kin},F}$ (MeV)	ϵ_T (μm)	ϵ_L (mm)	N_T (%)	$E_{\text{kin},F}$ (MeV)
	FC-RB8				FC-RB10			
0	300	1.5	100	73.8				
1	275	2.7	98	39.4				
2	213	5.9	94	32.7				
3	170	6.8	89	32.5				

4	138	12.4	82	31.4	140	1.5	100	36.4
5	103	20.6	74	16.9	124	2.0	99.6	25.1
6	81	25	61	14.7	99	3.8	97	14.3
7	60	32.7	53	13.3	82	5.0	88	13.0
8	51	43.6	47	14.0	60	7.1	82	8.1
9	41	48.4	37	12.4	46	9.7	72	8.3
10	33	66.1	32	8.8	34	17.9	64	6.3
11	30	82	29	11.2	24	35.3	60	6.1

The third element is the strong transverse space charge fields in the final cooling caused by the reduced transverse beam sizes $\sigma_{x,y}$. The non-linearity of these forces may lead to reductions of the dynamic aperture. The expected tune spread along the rectilinear and final cooling cells has been estimated analytically, based on the current cooling lattice properties.

The beam break-up instability generated by the resistive wall wake of the beam chambers was also estimated. Thanks to the large chamber radius the growth parameter for this instability is small. Moreover BNS (Balakin, Novokhatski and Smirnov) damping was not included in the estimation and should further mitigate this type of instability.

Fig. 15: Analytical estimate of the momentum spread from longitudinal space charge, relative to the initial beam momentum spread (left plot) and the tune spread from transverse space charge (right plot) along the rectilinear and final cooling.

3.5.5. Final considerations

Several challenges have been identified during the study which are listed below:

- Design of the charge separation, bunch merge and reacceleration systems was not progressed owing to a lack of available effort. The target performance was estimated based on simulations performed by US-MAP.
- The spent proton beam at the target was identified as presenting a significant source of highly penetrating radiation that may cause damage to downstream systems. Design of a proton beam extraction system is ongoing.
- Thermal expansion of liquid hydrogen absorbers under beam heating was identified as a technical challenge. This is viewed as a particular risk for low emittance beams, where energy

deposit is more tightly focused, and low energy beams, where energy is deposited in a much shorter distance.

- Beam loading of RF cavities was identified as requiring further study. This is a particular challenge in the rectilinear cooling system where frequencies can be relatively high.
- Integration of highly compact lattices, with very strong fields and high gradient cavities, will be a challenge in the rectilinear cooling system. This is actively studied by the Muon Cooling Cell integration task (WP8).

3.6. WP5 : HIGH ENERGY COMPLEX

WP5 is in charge of defining the layout of the chain of muon accelerators starting at the end of the muon cooling sections and down to the collider ring. This required setting up a new framework of simulations since the US-MAP was targeting a maximum energy of up to 6 TeV in the center of mass. Preliminary layouts however were generated resorting to the scheme of US-MAP and adapting them to the energy of 10 TeV. In addition, one of the main challenges of the collider, namely the high level of background to the experiments coming from products of muon decay, has been optimised through a detailed study of the Machine Detector Interface (MDI) section. The work of WP5 has been key to define first the tentative (ref) and then the preliminary [10] list of parameters published by MuCol.

3.6.1. Low-energy acceleration

The low energy section includes three sections: a single-pass linear pre-accelerator (PA) followed by a pair of multi-pass recirculating linacs (RLA). Previously, a dog-bone accelerator scheme was studied using different lattice configurations such as FODO, Triplet, Theoretical Minimum Emittance (TME) and Double Bend Achromat (DBA). Due to the need for strong focusing in the bending plane to minimize chromatic effects, a symmetrical lattice solution, which is obligatory for dog-bone, could not be found.

In the presented scenario, acceleration starts after final cooling at 255MeV and proceeds to 63GeV, where the beam is going to be injected into a first rapid cycling synchrotron. A schematic of the low energy section is shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16: Layout of a two-step-racetrack RLA complex. Pre-accelerator, race-track I and race-track II are stacked vertically; $\mu\pm$ beam is transported between the accelerator sections by the vertical dogleg.

The PA will use a lower frequency (88 MHz) than the following RLAs to ensure sufficient momentum acceptance for the long beam coming from the final cooling. It will additionally feature a 3rd harmonic cavity operating at 264MHz to minimise uncorrelated energy spread and low-energy acceleration.

A preliminary study for the pre-accelerator section was carried out to test the evaluation of the longitudinal phase space. It has been shown that an initial beam with an RMS length of 0.4m and an RMS energy spread of 5% can be accelerated by a linac with a length of about 800m to 1.5GeV with a final RMS bunch length of 40mm while maintaining the longitudinal emittance. If one requires higher frequencies than 88MHz in PA the bunch length needs to be shortened due to limitation in acceleration of RF waveform.

Fig. 17: Start-to-end Twiss functions along RLA2

A comprehensive study for RLA2 was carried out since the previous report. We used a slightly weak FODO chain in the linac to reduce chromatic effects at low energy, incorporating 2 quadrupoles and 2 sections of 3 superconducting LEP2 cavities. Vertical bending spreaders, which are fully normal conducting, are designed to match the beam to the linac as well as the relevant arcs with increasing energy. For the correction of second-order dispersion in the bending plane as well as to

minimise chromatic effects, a second-order achromatic line based on FODO without sextupoles is used for all eight arcs by adjusting the space between the magnets in the cell.

An initial bunch with 0.0225eV s longitudinal and $20\mu\text{m}$ transverse emittance could be accelerated from 5GeV to 63GeV while preserving longitudinal emittance, with less than 10% increase in transverse plane, and a better than 90% muon survival rate. Fig. 17 shows the linear lattice functions along RLA2.

In subsequent RLAs, superconducting accelerating cavities operating at 352MHz will be employed. The 1056MHz cavities are additionally foreseen to linearise the RF waveform to minimise the growth of uncorrelated energy spread in the beam. The use of different non-harmonic frequencies in the two acceleration sections requires that the distance between the muon and anti-muon bunches be adjusted with a magnetic array such as a chicane to match the acceleration frequency.

Fig. 18: RLA vertical spreader section before the matching section and injection into the arcs.

The arcs feature the same length and can, therefore, be stacked vertically in one tunnel. The arc magnets are superconducting to achieve the required bending strength in higher-energy passes. To achieve matching into the arc optics, a vertical spreader with fixed optics is planned to be used, which is presented in Fig. 18. This design achieves a transmission of 93% with a final transverse emittance of $21.3\mu\text{m}$ and a final longitudinal emittance of 0.025eV s , meeting the required target parameters. The target parameters for RLA2 are a transmission rate of 90%, a longitudinal emittance below 0.025eV s and a transverse emittance below $22.5\mu\text{m}$. Table 8 contains the main parameters for the simulated RLA2 and the predicted RLA1.

Table 8: Multi-pass recirculating linac parameters. The length of the linac refers to the length of a single linac section. The parameters for the PA (Pre-Accelerator) are not yet available and the ones of the RLA1 are temporary assumptions, as the detailed designs of both linacs were not performed yet. The arc lengths define the length of an individual return arc, while the linac length refers to the length of one straight section of the RLA

	RLA1		RLA2	
Initial energy [GeV]	1.25		5	
Final energy [GeV]	5		63	
Energy gain per pass [GeV]	0.85		13.5	
Frequency [MHz]	352	1056	352	1056
No. SRF cavities	36	4	600	80
RF length [m]	61.2	4	1020	68
RF gradient [MV/m]	15	25	15	25
Passes	4.5		4.5	
Linac length [m]	-		915	
Arc lengths [m]	-		~300	

3.6.2. Collective effects

The two Recirculating Linacs (RLA) will bring the muon bunches energy from 1.25GeV to 63GeV.

Beam-beam interactions will occur in each of the four droplet arcs and could lead to emittance growth and beam losses. Tracking simulations with Xsuite were performed for the RLA 1, assuming a linear transfer map between each beam-beam interaction point (IP). The beam-beam interaction is a non-linear effect and is modelled with Bassetti-Erskine formula, which assumes Gaussian profile for the transverse beam distribution. Simulations show a large emittance growth can occur if the phase advance between IPs is not carefully chosen. This emittance growth can be mitigated by introducing $\sim 1\text{m}$ of dispersion at the IPs. Combined with the proper choice of longitudinal and transverse phase advance between IPs, the emittance growth from beam-beam interaction can be kept below the percent level.

3.6.3. High Energy Acceleration

Once the muons have been pre-accelerated to an energy in the range of 63 GeV, two muon bunches must be brought simultaneously to an energy of up to 5 TeV. Several schemes, like fixed-field alternating gradient synchrotrons, have been considered. The most promising and straightforward accelerator type in that energy range is the rapid cycling synchrotron (RCS). A possible chain of acceleration based on RCSs has been studied and is sketched in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19: Sketch of the chain of rapid cycling-synchrotrons for the high-energy acceleration complex.

It combines fast acceleration with a cost-efficient implementation up to the highest particle energies. It moreover provides the necessary space for the large-scale RF system. Nonetheless, compared to existing conventional RCS, the ones for muons will be significantly larger, with much higher accelerating voltages per turn and a very low number of revolutions. To achieve extremely fast acceleration with ramp rates of several kT/s together with high average bending strength, fixed-field super-conducting and fast-ramping normal conducting magnets will be interleaved. The latter can then be driven from negative to positive saturation for a maximum bending field swing, $-B_{nc}$ to $+B_{nc}$. The hybrid RCS concept was inspired by the US MAP[23]. It is foreseen to accelerate two counter-rotating bunches with a repetition of 5 Hz. The green-field option, also suggested by the US MAP study, includes intermediate stages of 0.31 TeV, 0.75 TeV and 1.5 TeV to finally reach 5 TeV before injecting the muons into the dedicated collider ring. This scenario is illustrated in Fig. 19. The acceleration parameters of the RCS chain are given in Table 9. The bending in the first RCS is provided by normal conducting magnets only, while the RCS2 to RCS4 is planned with the hybrid bending scheme. In this configuration, the first two RCSs have the same circumference and layout, which allows their installation in the same ring tunnel. Such a magnet layout allows for a fast acceleration ramp, provided by the normal conducting magnet while simultaneously achieving a high average magnetic field. As a result, high energies can be reached in a relatively compact machine.

Table 9: RCS acceleration chain key parameters

Parameter	Unit	RCS1	RCS2	RCS3	RCS4
Hybrid RCS	-	no	yes	yes	yes
Repetition rate	Hz	5	5	5	5
Circumference	m	5990	5990	10700	35000
Injection energy	GeV	63	314	750	1500
Extraction energy	GeV	314	750	1500	5000
Energy ratio	-	5.0	2.4	2.0	3.3

Assumed survival rate	-	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Cumulative survival rate	-	0.9	0.81	0.729	0.6561
Acceleration time	ms	0.34	1.10	2.37	6.37
Revolution period	μ s	20	20	36	117
Number of turns	-	17	55	66	55
Required energy gain/turn	GeV	14.8	7.9	11.4	63.6
Average accel. gradient	MV/m	2.44	1.33	1.06	1.83
Number of bunches per species		1	1	1	1
Inj. bunch population	E12	2.7	2.4	2.2	2
Ext. bunch population	E12	2.4	2.2	2	1.8
Beam current per bunch	mA	21.67	19.5	9.88	2.75
Beam power	MW	640	310	225	350
Vert. norm. emittance	μ m	25	25	25	25
Horiz. norm. emittance	μ m	25	25	25	25
Long. norm. emittance	eVs	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025
Bunch length at injection	ps	31	30	23	13
Bunch length at ejection	ps	20	24	19	9
Straight section length	m	2335	2335	3977	10367
Length pulsed dipole magnets	m	3654	2539	4366	20376
Length steady dipole magnets	m	-	1115	2358	4257

Max. pulsed dipole field	T	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
Max. steady dipole field	T	-	10	10	16
Ramp rate	T/s	4200	3282	1519	565

3.6.4. Collective effects for RCSs

To meet the muon survival rate target in the high-energy acceleration chain, large acceleration gradients are required in the Rapid Cycling Synchrotrons. This requires a large number of RF cavities able to reach a high accelerating gradient. For example in RCS 1 the energy gain per turn must be 14.7 GeV to lose only 10% of the intensity to muon decay. To reach this acceleration, $O(700)$ TESLA superconducting RF cavities operating at 1.3 GHz [24], with an individual accelerating gradient of 30 MV/m will be needed. High-order modes (HOMs) in the cavities will generate short and long-range wakefields which combined to the high muon bunch intensities could disrupt the beam motion and lead to emittance blow-up and particle losses. Additionally, the fast ramping of the normal conducting magnet in the RCS constrains the vacuum chamber design in order to minimize eddy current induced power losses. Ceramic must be used as the main bulk material of the chamber, together with an inner metallic RF shielding to reduce impedance effects. An initial radial build of the vacuum chamber is proposed and pictured in Fig. 20, meeting constraints set from magnets, powering, vacuum and impedance.

Impedance models have been developed for the four RCS of the high energy acceleration chain. They include the RF cavity HOMs and the normal conducting magnets vacuum chamber design. Two types of TESLA cavity were considered: the classic TESLA cavity and the Low-Loss type cavity [25]. Fig. 21 shows on the left-hand side the wakefield generated by the HOMs of a single TESLA cavity or a Low Loss cavity, highlighting the reduction in wake strength obtained by using the classic TESLA cavity. On the right-hand side, the figure shows the simulated transverse dipolar impedance of a 1m- long section of a normal conducting magnet vacuum chamber for different RF shielding thicknesses.

The ceramic chamber introduces large resonances in the impedance that are reduced by the RF shield. Macroparticle tracking simulations using the Xsuite and PyHEADTAIL codes were performed to evaluate the impact of impedance on single bunch transverse coherent stability, from injection in the RCS 1 through ejection of the RCS 4. The effect of an initial transverse offset of the beam at the injection in each ring was also included. Instability mitigation measures such as a transverse damper and chromaticity were also investigated. Simulations found out that a positive chromaticity of $Q' = +20$ is required in the four RCS to preserve the transverse beam emittance. An initial transverse offset resulting from injection jitter can also be tolerated, up to $10\mu\text{m}$ in each RCS.

Fig. 20: Proposed radial build of the RCS 1 normal conducting magnets vacuum chamber.

3.6.5. FFAs as an alternative

Muon acceleration by an FFA (Fixed-Field Alternating Gradient) accelerator has been investigated for many years since it appeared in the neutrino factory proposal in the 1990s. Recent developments in FFA optics, especially of vertical excursion FFAs, added significant advantages in using an FFA as the muon accelerator. Although there are not many FFA accelerators even for accelerating ordinary particles like protons, an FFA scheme could be an alternative option to an RCS.

An FFA uses DC magnets, as the name indicates. That means both advantages and disadvantages. From the operational point of view, it is ideal for acceleration of short-lived particles because there is no change of magnetic field according to the beam momentum. On the other hand, FFAG magnet apertures are relatively large and that is the main technical challenge, especially with superconducting magnets where the wide aperture means large stored energy.

The optics of a vertical excursion FFA (vFFA) is fully coupled in two transverse planes. The optics design and dynamics analysis are much more complex than the more common horizontal excursion FFA (hFFA), and that in fact discourages consideration of a vFFA as an option.

Recent work provides an analytical model for vFFA optics, offering insight into parameter dependence and potential optimization for muon colliders.

The analytic model has been used to develop example parameter sets for equivalent vFFA rings to RCS1 and RCS2, showing that vFFA rings with equivalent footprints to the RCS baselines can achieve stable optics whilst maintaining realistic design constraints. In particular, the movement of the orbit from injection to extraction (the excursion) is now less than 120mm in each case, and the peak dipole fields on orbit are maintained below 8T in the early-stage vFFA and below 16T in the final-stage vFFA.

3.6.6. Collider

The muon collider ring has been designed with two straight Interaction Regions (IRs) located at opposite positions, where the two counter-rotating muon bunches collide where the detectors are installed. The arc consists of several components: a Chromatic Compensation Sections (CCS) adjacent to the IRs to correct chromatic aberrations generated by strong focusing next to the detectors, followed by matching sections connecting to regular arc cells, which are periodic focusing structure over most of the arc.

The primary aim of the muon collider ring design is to maximize the luminosity to the experiments, taking into account the characteristics of the injected beam as determined by the ionization cooling channels and various acceleration stages. Additional constraints are generated by muon decay products. The resulting heat loads for the cryogenic system and the radiation damage to magnets are mitigated by Tungsten absorbers. Unwanted signals to detectors are suppressed by the Machine Detector Interface (MDI) and by making use of tungsten absorbers and other shielding materials.

Neutrinos generate radiation at the location where they reach the Earth's surface, which requires careful evaluations and has to be taken into account in the machine design in order to ensure that effective doses to general public remain negligible and below the dose objective of $10\mu\text{Sv/year}$ aimed at by CERN. A large number of neutrinos will be generated in the direction given by the long straight section housing the experiments, developing a significant dose where they reach Earth's surface. This results on the one hand in an opportunity for an experiment profiting from the large neutrino flux, and on the other hand the corresponding flux site should be owned by the organization operating the collider and fenced. Radiation levels from the other parts of the machine will be limited by reducing the length of short straight sections in the arc to the minimum. Thus, combined functions quadrupoles and higher-order multipoles will be used instead of normal straight quadrupoles and multipoles and interconnect regions between magnets have to be minimized. In addition, peak doses will be reduced by periodic deformations in vertical direction of the whole machine as well known as "machine wobbling". These deformations change the vertical beam direction within a range of $\pm 1\text{mrad}$, distributing the radiation generated by neutrinos over a larger surface area. This requires a high precision mechanical system to implement the required displacements of the magnets and additional horizontal magnetic fields for vertical deflections in the magnet design. If the collider ring is not located deep underground, horizontal closed orbit deformations (inside the aperture without deformations of the whole machine in horizontal direction) are required in addition to mitigating neutrino radiation hot spots located in the direction of short straights between arc magnets.

Magnets with as high field strength as possible are required. Strong chromatic aberrations making the optics design very challenging are generated with the highest possible gradients and would further increase with lower gradients. Strong dipolar fields in other sections result in a shorter circumference and revolution time, such that less muons decay between bunch encounters and luminosity increases. As the length of straight sections outside the one housing the IPs must be minimized, combined function quadrupoles and sextupoles are used.

Fig. 21: Left: wakefield strength generated by the HOMs of a TESLA (blue) and a Low Loss (orange) 1.3GHz superconducting RF cavity. Right: real part of the horizontal dipolar impedance of the RCS normal conducting magnet vacuum chamber, for different RF shielding thickness, from no shielding (blue) to 1mm thick copper shielding (purple).

3.7. WP6: RADIOFREQUENCY SYSTEMS

3.7.1. Baseline concept of the RF system for acceleration to the High Energy Complex

A survey of existing high-frequency SRF cavities at 1.3 GHz was conducted at the onset of the reporting period, and an analysis of the quantities of interest (QOI) for the fundamental (FM) and higher-order modes (HOM) was performed for all cavities of interest. However, no clear advantages of any design could be identified. Subsequently, one of the designs was scaled to different frequencies and numbers of cavity cells to investigate the impact on the cavity QOIs. Preliminary numerical calculations were performed for the power requirements in the FM and HOM couplers, but no permissive values were identified.

A preliminary calculation of RF-system parameters for the greenfield study was conducted, based on the RF-system planned for the international linear collider (ILC), using the TESLA cavity as a baseline with an accelerating gradient of 30 MV/m. The calculation formulas of the parameters were integrated into the RCS parameters Python module, which allows for the simultaneous optimization of high-level, magnet, optics and RF parameters. A parameter set for the rapid cycling synchrotron chain and the RLA2 was provided for the MuCol parameter report, and the ESPPU input document.

The RCS parameters module was used to calculate a preliminary set of parameters for the installation of the Muon Collider in the CERN tunnel infrastructure. To complement the beam dynamics simulations performed by WP5, a transient beam loading simulation was performed for the cavity voltage in the RCS chain. This study revealed the need for a different detuning scheme than initially anticipated.

3.7.2. Baseline concept of the RF system for the Muon Cooling Complex

The focus of this task, led in conjunction by INFN and CEA, is to establish a conceptual design of the RF systems for the cooling section, based on a consistent set of parameters for all RF cavities and associated systems to be integrated into the cooling cells obtained from inputs given by WP4 and WP8. For the muon cooling section, one challenge already pointed out in the preliminary MAP study, is to achieve gradients of the order of 30 MV/m in RF cavities that will be placed in high magnetic fields and explore whether it is possible to push these values at safer and upper levels. The fact that cavities are immersed in high magnetic field excludes the possibility to use superconducting materials to achieve the high electric fields required, therefore copper is considered as bulk material.

The work achieved in this task was developed in close collaboration with the CERN team working in the IMCC and started from the study of a single cell cavity at 704 MHz. After a few iterations with WP4 to discuss the best tradeoff between the various constraints posed by emittance reduction efficiency, geometrical parameters and RF power, the study has been now focused on a three cells cavity, in particular for a cell of type B5, which is the same chosen for the integration studies of WP8. One of the main issues is how to couple the RF power in the restrained space available. While ideally beam dynamics would be more efficient if every cell had its own RF power coupler, space constraints impose the use of a single couple for the three cell RF structure, and to couple the cells among them either magnetically or electrically. A magnetic coupling tends to maximize the gradient, but requires the presence of metallic windows between cells and slots to connect the cells as close as possible to the equator, where the magnetic field is maximum, leading to thermomechanical and integration difficulties that have to be studied in details to ensure the feasibility of this solution. Electrically coupled cells on the other hand can be designed to minimize the surface electric field, responsible of breakdown issues, but reduce also the total accelerating field for the same RF power. Studies are therefore ongoing to establish the suitability of both options.

From the first simulations it turns out that beam loading could be a limit for the performance of the structure, and therefore more detailed studies are necessary to propose appropriate mitigating actions.

Concerning the use of RF cavities in high magnetic fields, significant efforts have been devoted to solving this problem by the US-MAP programme [26]. Two solutions have proven effective, the use of Be surfaces to reduce the Secondary Emission Yield (SEY) and increase the resilience of the surfaces (an 805 MHz cavity with Be windows was constructed and tested in Fermilab [27]). The second solution was the use of high-pressure low-Z gas (gaseous H₂) to significantly reduce the mean free path of electrons that are the source of the breakdown. Both solutions provided high electric field and sufficient resilience to breakdown, but their applicability to a real machine equipped with several thousands of those cavities has to be assessed from the mechanical, safety and cost point of view. Another promising technology is the so called C³ technology [28]. Cavities cooled at liquid N₂ temperature have been found to have a reduced breakdown rate, however they have never been tested in magnetic field. A real scale test is being prepared in the SLAC laboratory, and will probably take place in 2026.

The IMCC has proposed a muon ionization cooling demonstrator to prove the six-dimensional emittance reduction, and has adopted the design of the cooling cell being designed by WP8 as baseline [29]. WP6 is performing the studies of the RF cavity to be used by WP8. A conceptual RF design of a 704 MHz copper cavity, closed by two beryllium windows at both cavity irises, as depicted in Fig. 1, is currently under consideration [30]. The cavity design has been performed based on beam dynamics specifications detailed in [18]. Results of the RF-thermo-mechanical analyses for this conceptual cavity design are reported in [30].

The main RF figures of merit of the cavity have been calculated in CST Studio Suite [31]. Additionally, thermo-mechanical and Lorentz Force Detuning (LFD) simulations have been conducted in COMSOL Multiphysics [32], considering a nominal gradient of 22.5 MV/m.

Fig. 22: Design of the 704 MHz cavity for muon cooling.

The geometry was optimized to maximize the cavity shunt impedance to reduce surface losses on cavity walls and Be-windows. The peak surface electric field was also minimized to limit the risk of RF-breakdown. The main results of the RF-thermo-mechanical analysis are summarized as follows:

- The maximum surface electric field is 24.12 MV/m, while the peak surface magnetic field is 53.58 mT for the considered accelerating gradient of 20.26 MV/m.
- The average power is 51.15 W. The resulting peak temperature on the cavity is 304.8 K, under forced cooling condition of the external cavity walls ($T_0 = 300$ K), and it is located at the centre of the Be-window.
- The maximum radiation pressure of 11 mbar is detected on the window walls. The maximum von Mises stress is 125 MPa and is localized on the edge of the window. Despite being twice lower than Be yield stress, it might lead to window rupture under the fatigue induced by Lorentz force detuning and heating.
- The mechanical displacement, resulting from the combined effect of thermal expansion and radiation pressure, is 881 μm at the centre of the cavity window. This mechanical deformation shifts the cavity resonance frequency of -0.909 MHz, which is significantly higher than the cavity bandwidth.

Fig. 23: Three-cell cavity for the cooling cell of WP8.

The studies of the single cell 704 MHz were propaedeutic to the study of a multicell cavity to be used for the cooling cell. Some modifications were necessary to the profile of the cell to develop a full-scale structure for a 3-cells. The RF performances were kept very similar to the one of the single cell cavity. The RF power coupler, housed in the central RF cell, has been optimized in performance, showing the possibility to drive the structure with a limited RF power (less than 5 MW). The RF cells are magnetically coupled through 4 slots in the iris.

The resulting structure is shown in Fig. 23.

3.7.3. Breakdown mitigation studies for cavities of the muon cooling cells

The goal of this task, led by CEA in conjunction with INFN as far as experimental activities are concerned, is to study and enhance the present comprehension of the intrinsic concepts that influence the break down rate of RF cavities submitted to strong magnetic fields. As a starting point it was planned to extend existing theoretical studies, and with additional inputs from previous experimental studies at CERN for CLIC and FermiLab for MAP, as well as from additional tests performed in the scope of this task, realistic solutions to mitigate the breakdown and provide guidance for the design and the fabrication of high gradient RF cavities that stand strong magnetic fields will be proposed.

The work achieved in this task includes simulations studies with CST PIC code, describing the influence of strong magnetic field on the trajectories of field emitted electrons. Further work is ongoing to describe the phenomena resulting from the electron collision on the surface. Another hypothesis to be explored is that the breakdown enhancement in presence of strong magnetic field arises at the initial electron emission itself rather than at the electron collision on cavity surface.

In parallel, the possibility of carrying out experimental tests is being studied. A facility, which will be operative next February at INFN, is aimed to verify the breakdown behavior of samples of different materials with specific surface treatments. The samples may be driven by a pulsed DC high voltage power supply subsystem operating at 10 kV allowing to reach fields of the order of tens of MV/m, while being subjected to a 1 T magnetic field.

A more complex set up has been designed at INFN-Lasa for a RF Test stand facility based on single RF cavities at 3 GHz and operated in a magnetic field up to 5 T. This setup will act as a second stage of test using the solutions validated in the test stand. A mockup of a true 3 GHz RF cavity has been designed during the first 12 months.

3.7.4. Baseline concept of high efficiency and high-power RF sources for the muon collider

The aim of this task, led by University of Lancaster, is to provide a baseline concept for the RF sources needed for the muon collider that will require higher RF power than is currently possible with commercially available sources.

The ionization cooling section requires very high power, relatively low frequency RF sources. A nominal RF peak power per klystron of 24 MW has been set as a goal to minimise the size of the klystron gallery, and lower costs. Klystrons of this power exist at frequencies above 1 GHz, but are very large, for example the 1 GHz 20 MW Klystron prototypes for CLIC produced by THALES (TH1803) and Canon (E37503) have a 1.5 metre RF circuit, plus additional length for the gun and collector makes the klystron well over 2 metres in height. It is not trivial to scale a klystron to other

frequencies as the bunching would change requiring significant redesign, and the length is inversely proportional to frequency. This would mean a 352 MHz klystron would be three times longer if directly scaled making the active length 4.5 metres.

Klystrons do exist of reasonable length around 250-400 MHz at powers around 350 kW, for example the HL-LHC Klystron delivers 368 kW and has an active length of around 1.5 metres for the RF circuit. We could combine several beams, using common cavities for each beam known as a multi-beam klystron to reach 24 MW but this would require 65 beamlets. Increasing the voltage from 58 kV to bring up the beam power to reduce the required number of beams, unfortunately increases the length of the tube as the electrons travel faster, and increasing the beamlet current above the current 9 A will cause a reduction in efficiency.

In order to increase the beam voltage without increasing the length we must therefore use a new concept, known as a two-stage klystron. In these devices the beam is initially at a lower voltage (in this case ~25 kV) which slows the electrons down, making the tube much shorter. Then after the beam is bunched we post-accelerate to 140 kV to have sufficient beam power to generate 24 MW in the output cavity. Previously two-stage klystrons have been designed for CLIC at 1 GHz, 20 MW which reduced the active length down to 900 mm.

As part of MuCol, we have applied well known scaling procedures, PSP method, to scale the CLIC design to the desired frequency and power for Muon Cooling, 352 MHz and 24 MW respectively. Initially a 20 beam version at 16 MW was generated as the 30 beam 24 MW scaled tube had an issue with reflected electrons as the RF cavity is not scaled exactly. The comparison is shown below.

Fig. 24: Applegate diagram and harmonic currents, from KlyC, for the CLIC two-stage MBK (left) and the scaled version at 352 MHz 16 MW

The output power roughly is proportional to $P = (NI)^2 R/Q M^2 Q_{\text{ext}}$, where N is the number of beams, I is the beamlet current, R/Q is the cavity normalised impedance, M is the gap coupling factor, and Q_{ext} is the external Q factor of the output cavity. In order to generate 24 MW the beamlet current had to increase from 6 A to 7 A, and to avoid having very large gaps at 352 MHz the gap coupling factor also increases. To compensate for this we have to decrease the R/Q or Q_{ext} , as Q_{ext} was already very low it was necessary to decrease R/Q instead.

In order to scale to 24 MW we needed to look at the RF cavity in more detail. To fit in 30 beams we can either have a single row of beams in a larger cavity, or two rows in a smaller cavity. Moving to two rows results in a higher impedance cavity which is normally an advantage in klystron design, but as already mentioned we need to reduce the R/Q . In addition with two rows each row experiences a different RF voltage. As a result we decided to use a single row. We then reoptimized the klystron design in KlyC by varying the frequency and position of the intermediate cavities that cause the beam to bunch. Initially the klystron was optimised to maximise the harmonic current presented to the

output cavity. Then the gap length and the external Q factor of the output was varied to maximise efficiency while avoiding reflected electrons. It was found that the gap needed to be 140 mm long to reach 24 MW without reflected electrons.

The final design produced 23.88 MW with 80.4% efficiency from a 140.4 kV beam with 30 beamlets each with 7.07 Amps of current. The beamlet radius was 9.75 mm making the average current density 2.63 A/cm². The filling factor was kept to the industry standard 0.65. The active length of the RF circuit is around 1.9 metres.

3.8. WP7: MAGNET SYSTEMS

All the magnet systems in the Muon Collider configuration studied within the scope of MuCol have been analysed, in discussion with beam physics, to understand the demands on performance and operating conditions. This has led to a consolidated view of magnet specifications and challenges. A good impression of the challenges at hand can be gained from the summary of magnet development targets reported in Table 10. The values there have evolved beyond initial review of the configuration of US-MAP, to take into account both the changes in beam physics specifications, as well as the progress in conceptual and engineering magnet design. Table 10 is only a simplified view, it lacks many details of the actual machine configuration, and aspects such as field quality, still under discussion. It is nonetheless useful to give a compact view of the exceptional envelope of performance to be achieved.

Table 10: Summary of magnet development targets for the Muon Collider.

	Target, decay and capture	6D cooling	Final cooling	Rapid cycling synchrotron		Collider ring			
Magnet type (-)	Solenoid	Solenoid	Solenoid	NC Dipole	SC Dipole	Dipole	Dipole	Dipole	Quadrupole
SC material options (-)	HTS	HTS/LTS ⁽²⁾	HTS	N/A	HTS	Nb-Ti	Nb ₃ Sn	HTS	HTS
Aperture (mm)	1400	60...800 ⁽³⁾	50	30x100	30x100	160	160	140	140
Length (m)	19	0.08...0.3 ⁽³⁾	0.5...1 ⁽⁴⁾	5	2	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	4...6 ⁽⁴⁾	3...9 ⁽⁴⁾
Number of magnets (-)	20	2 x 3030	20	7000 ⁽⁶⁾	3000 ⁽⁶⁾	1250 ⁽⁶⁾	1250 ⁽⁶⁾	1250 ⁽⁶⁾	28
Bore Field/Gradient (T)/(T/m)	20	2.6...17.9 ⁽³⁾	> 40	± 1.8 ⁽⁵⁾	10	5	11	14	300
Ramp-rate (T/s)	SS	SS	SS	4200...500 ⁽⁷⁾	SS	SS	SS	SS	SS
Stored energy (MJ)	1400	5...75	4	0.03	3.4	5	20	24	60
Heat load (W/m)	2 ⁽¹⁾	TBD	TBD	1200	5	5	5	10	10
Radiation dose (MGy)	80	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	30	30	30	30
Operating temperature (K)	20	4.5...20	4.5	300	20	4.5	4.5	20	4.5...20

As it is clear from above, HTS magnet technology was identified as a crucial technology enabler for a Muon Collider. Having identified the main specifications, concepts and challenges the next step which has been completed was the conceptual design of selected magnets representative of the above challenges. We have progressed in particular in the areas described below, each of them representing a major challenge in superconducting and accelerator magnet technology.

3.8.1. Solenoids

3.8.1.1. Target solenoid

The solenoid that hosts the target and capture channel, where the muon beam is produced, pose the first grand challenge. The magnetic field profile along the axis of the channel has a shape derived from studies of optimal generation and capture, with peak field of 20 T on the target, and a decay to approximately 1.5 T at the exit of the channel, over a total length of approximately 18 m. The characteristic length of the field change is about 2.5 m, i.e. much larger than the gyration radius of the muons in the field so that the beam expands adiabatically in the channel. Such field profile can be generated by an assembly of 23 HTS modules, shown schematically in Fig. 1. In the same figure, the

Fig. 25: Comparison (to scale) of the solenoid coils of the target, decay and capture channel of a Muon Collider, as produced by the MAP study (top) and resulting from the optimization of an all-HTS solution (bottom).

solution found in the MuCol study is compared to the configuration that was proposed by US-MAP. The HTS solenoid has a mass of 100 tons and a stored energy of 1.4 GJ, about half the mass and stored energy of the US-MAP configuration. The electrical power consumption, estimated at 1 MW, is reduced by one order of magnitude with respect to the configuration that was proposed by US-MAP.

3.8.1.2. 6D cooling solenoid

The 6D “beam cooling” process occurs over a 1 km long sequence of tightly integrated absorbers, alternating polarity solenoids, and RF cavities. The US-MAP design study provided a baseline configuration of a 6D cooling channel, consisting of 826 cooling cells over an approximate 970 m distance, with a total of almost 3000 solenoids. These cells can be divided into 12 unique types termed A1-A4 and B1-B8. Each cell type contains between 2 to 6 solenoids, with a total of 18 unique solenoid types. We performed an analysis on these solenoids, considering them operating individually and within their respective lattice. We found substantial stresses (large average hoop, higher than 300

MPa and tensile radial stress, in excess of 50 MPa), forces (37 MN axial force), and quench management challenges (energy densities up to 91 MJ/m³ in a single coil).

Such values suggest that the solenoid configuration may need further optimization to reach engineering level. This is a non-trivial task, because the beam optics in the solenoids of the muon cooling channel is far from being formalized as well as that of a collider, and any change in magnet engineering may have dramatic effects on beam transmission. Recognizing this challenge, we have developed solenoid design rules that implement simple engineering limits on operating margin, stress and stored energy density. These rules are integrated already at the stage of the beam optics design, thus anticipating magnet performance limits. Having the design rules as part of the beam optics optimization has reduced the iteration time and improved effectiveness of each design optimization. In parallel, we have developed numerical optimization tools which can scan design variants and improve the solenoid configuration given a desired field profile. These tools allow to converge to optimal engineering solutions once the initial solenoid configuration is close enough to being feasible.

We have applied the above procedure to the new optics recently developed for the 6D cooling channel. This optics configuration has a total of 3030 solenoids in each 6D cooling chain, with a peak field on-axis broadly increasing from 2.6 T to 17.9 T. There are 26 unique solenoid types, with bore radii ranging from 25 mm to 400 mm, lengths from 75 mm to 287 mm, and current densities from 58 A/mm² to 327 A/mm². The solenoids experience substantial peak fields at the conductor (up to 19 T), large stresses and forces. However, these values are not far off target limits, and can be optimized further. The initial solenoid configurations also exhibit tight spacing, and needs to better factor in room for RF structure and waveguides. These additional parameters (magnet spacing, RF required spacing), will be factored into the next iteration of the beam optics optimization.

3.8.1.3. Final cooling solenoid

Among the solenoids in the cooling channel, the final cooling solenoids are most challenging in terms of field performance, with a target of 40 T or higher. The bore dimension is relatively small, 50 mm, which makes them an ideal development vehicle to implement new technology such as non-insulated windings, and probe performance limits. Indeed, this solenoid is an ideal vehicle for R&D, allowing fast turn-around models and tests that are relevant to magnets of larger dimension, such as the solenoids for the 6D cooling. This is why we have advanced very swiftly in the conceptual and engineering design of the 40 T final cooling solenoid.

We have proposed a conceptual design at the early stage of the study. The solenoid concept is based on soldered single pancakes, stacked with stress-management plates, and joined electrically. The coil is pre-compressed radially by a solid mechanical structure, supporting the electro-magnetic loads, and necessary to avoid tensile stress in the coil at nominal operating conditions.

The concept for the final cooling solenoid is shown schematically in Fig. M2, and it was developed at the outset of the study profiting from experience in other fields of science and societal applications. In the past twelve months we have focused on the development of engineering solutions for the realization. Fig. M2 shows 46 identical modular pancakes and three pairs of thicker single pancakes at both ends of the solenoid.

Fig. 26: Cross-section of the 40 T solenoid; the arrows indicate the axial and radial Lorentz forces acting on each pancake. The lengths of the radial arrows have been scaled down by a factor of 3

3.8.2. Accelerator magnet and powering systems

The largest number and most challenging magnets of the acceleration chain are those in the Rapid Cycled Synchrotrons (RCS) and Hybrid Ramped Synchrotrons (HCS). Among the several configurations studied, we have settled on common specifications for the dipole magnets of all stages, namely:

- Resistive dipoles with 1.8 T peak field and 30 mm (H) x 100 mm (W) rectangular aperture. These dipoles are pulsed with ms time scale at a frequency of 5 Hz. In the RCS they are ramped from injection to peak field (two quadrant), while in HCS they swing from negative to positive peak field (four quadrant);
- Superconducting dipoles with 10 T peak field and the same 30 mm (H) x 100 mm (W) rectangular aperture. These dipoles operate in steady state and provide the field offset for the HCS.

Both magnet types require field homogeneity in the range of few 10^{-4} in the good field region. Quadrupole magnets are still a subject of study, whereby we are scanning designs producing gradients in the range of 30 T/m in an aperture in the range of 40 mm to 80 mm, as discussed later.

The above magnet specifications require care and optimal design, and possibly better knowledge of magnetic and resistive properties of materials in the range of ramp-rates and frequencies required, but they appear well within the capabilities of present magnet technology. In fact, the main design driver for RCS and HCS is the management of the magnetic energy and reactive power, which should be highly efficient to minimize losses and very precise to meet beam performance specifications. To set orders of magnitude, the stored energy of a resistive magnet with the above characteristics is of the order of 6 kJ/m. The RCS have lengths in the range of 7 km to 27 km, and the total stored magnetic energy will hence be in the range of 30 MJ to 120 MJ (considering a dipole filling factor of 0.75).

Pulsing these circuits in the range of fractions of ms to ten ms will hence involve managing reactive powers in the range of tens of GW.

3.8.2.1. Resistive accelerator magnets and powering systems

To power the resistive magnets of RCS and HCS we have chosen a solution relying on resonant power converters and capacitor-based energy storage. This system allows to reach the desired combination of field, aperture and fast ramping, managing efficiently the reactive power. Fig. 27 shows the circuits to be used for unipolar or bipolar resonance. The unipolar resonance is used in case of the RCS configuration (two quadrants), i.e. when only pulsed resistive dipoles are considered, whereas the bipolar circuit is considered for the HCS configuration (four quadrants).

Fig. 27: Bipolar and Unipolar switched reluctance circuits.

We have explored several alternatives for the resistive dipole designs. The analysis performed mainly aimed at limiting the magnet stored energy, as this limits the reactive power required from the power converter during fast ramps and reduces the size of the energy storage. To investigate optimal magnet configurations for the RCS resistive dipole magnets, three geometric designs were considered, namely the hourglass, the window-frame, and the H-type. The best configurations found are shown schematically in Fig. 28. These configurations were optimized to minimize stored energy, subject to the constraint of achieving a specified magnetic flux density in the magnet air gap. The optimization procedure involved varying the peak engineering current density in the coils from 10 to 20 A/mm². The optimization uses an interactive routine based on Matlab for the optimizer part and FEMM for the 2D magnetic field and loss analysis. The routine scans geometric and electric variables and computes the electromagnetic field, searching for the configuration with minimum cost function, which is a weighted sum of stored energy, difference from the specified 1.8 T bore field, and field errors. Work is in progress in the design of the quadrupoles, the evaluation of AC loss during ramps, 3D effects, and global optimization of the magnet and power converter systems, including energy storage.

Fig. 28: Summary of the optimized geometries (the cross sections are to scale): a) Hourglass, $J = 10 \text{ A/mm}^2$, b) Window-frame WF#1, $J = 10 \text{ A/mm}^2$, c) Window-frame WF#1M, $J = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$, d) H-type HM, $J = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$, e) Window-frame WF#3, $J = 20 \text{ A/mm}^2$.

3.8.2.2. Superconducting accelerator dipoles

In parallel to the work on the normal-conducting pulsed magnets, we are progressing with the design of the superconducting magnets of the hybrid cycled synchrotrons (HCS). These magnets provide a field offset, and allow using the full field swing of the normal conducting magnets, from negative to positive field values, effectively making the synchrotrons shorter. The work has focused on HTS dipoles, operated in gaseous helium (10 K to 20 K) generating a 10 T steady state field in a rectangular aperture identical to that of the resistive dipole magnets, i.e. 30 mm x 100 mm. The choice of HTS

was driven by the intent to have a large operating margin and reduce consumption, especially in light of the effect of the bursts of muon decay that will cause periodic heating of the magnets. Also, operation at temperature significantly higher than liquid helium will ease the engineering of the transitions from resistive to superconducting magnets that takes place in each cell.

Fig. 29: Conceptual design of a 10 T HTS, 30 mm x 100 mm aperture dipole for the hybrid cycled synchrotrons.

3.8.2.3. Task 7.4: Collider magnets (INFN)

The magnets in the collider are the final big challenge that we have identified. Besides the difficulty in the magnet technology, muon beams require optics solutions that are far from standard practice, and integrating the specifications from beam optics poses an additional challenge. In order to provide quick feedbacks to the beam dynamics, cryogenics and energy deposition study requirements, an analytic evaluation of the maximum magnet performances as a function of the magnet aperture was performed. This preparatory work has then led to the choice of specific design points for the main dipoles and IR quadrupoles of the collider, which we have used to initiate conceptual and engineering design of the collider magnets.

To evaluate the maximum dipolar field or quadrupolar field gradient obtainable, a sector coil approximation was assumed, and all the most important constraints were included in the calculation, namely:

- Margin on the load line;
- Feasibility of the protection system;
- Mechanics;
- Cost.

The result of this analysis are “A-B” plots of maximum aperture for a given field, and “A-G” plots of maximum aperture for a given gradient, satisfying all requirements above. We report in Fig. 30 (A-B and A-G plots for Nb3Sn operated at 4.5 K, 400 kEUR/m cost limit), Fig. 31 (A-B plots for

REBCO dipoles operated at 4.5 K, 10 K and 20 K, 400 kEUR/m cost limit) and Fig. 32 (A-G plots for REBCO quadrupoles operated at 4.5 K, 10 K and 20 K, 800 kEUR/m cost limit).

Fig. 30: A-B plot for dipoles and A-G plot for quadrupoles built with Nb₃Sn and operated at 4.5 K.

Fig. 31: A-B plot for dipoles built with REBCO and operated at 4.5 K, 10 K and 20 K.

Fig. 32: A-G plot for quadrupoles built with REBCO and operated at 4.5 K, 10 K and 20 K.

For NbTi, the same analysis performed for other superconducting materials has been carried out. While this material does not achieve the required performance for a 10 TeV collider, it remains a viable alternative for a 3 TeV collider and provides an excellent reference for the work performed. Fig. 33 shows the A-B and A-G plots for NbTi magnets, assuming an operating temperature of 4.5 K.

Fig. 33: A-B plot for dipoles and A-G plot for quadrupoles built with NbTi and operated at 4.5 K.

The minimum apertures of the arc dipoles have been obtained from considerations of beam optics, impedance, radiation shielding, cryogenics and vacuum integration. In particular, the magnet aperture in the collider arc needs to be at least 158 mm for a cold mass at 4.5 K and 138 mm for a cold mass at 20 K. Using the above plots, we see that a dipole built with Nb3Sn, with an aperture of 158 mm, operated at 4.5 K, can reach fields of the order of 11 T. The same evaluation of a dipole built with REBCO, with an aperture of 138 mm, operated at 20 K, can reach fields of 14 T. We have hence set these as magnet performance targets representative of the challenges and pushing the limit of present technology. We note at this point that these magnet performance targets imply dipole coil dimensions that are significantly larger than what has been done in HL-LHC, and what is planned for FCC. Typically, the stored energy is a factor three to four larger. For the 3 TeV stage, using Nb-Ti at 4.5 K, a field of 5 T appears within reach.

The quadrupole performance limits are especially crucial for the IR, which is a major challenge of a muon collider. We see from the plots above that the performance limits follow an approximate dependence in the form $A = B_{\text{peak}}/G$, where the parameter B_{peak} is approximately 5 T for Nb-Ti, 10 T for Nb3Sn and 15 T for REBCO. The quadrupole magnets used in the present IR 10 TeV optics scale with a similar dependence, and we argue that developing a quadrupole of this class would be relevant to the whole IR. In this case we can focus on the largest gradient magnet, 300 T/m, which requires an aperture in the range of 140 mm.

3.8.3. Coordination and communication

Besides the work on coordinating efforts and communicating results, Task 7.1 has progressed in a summary of technology and proposal for future R&D. Using the results of the design work, summarised above, we have identified the main technology gaps, which is a key information to formulate an R&D plan beyond MuCol. We report in Fig. 34 a graphical representation of the present TRL for the various magnet and powering systems of a muon collider. This representation can be used to define the scale and type of R&D required, whether still at the level of small-scale demonstrators and models, when the estimated TRL is at the level of 4 to 5, or rather towards full-scale prototypes, for values of TRL 6 and higher.

Fig. 34: Summary of estimated TRL for the magnets of the muon collider

3.9. WP8: COOLING CELL INTEGRATION

The purpose of a cooling cell is to reduce the transverse and longitudinal emittance of the muon beam before acceleration. The muon beam is generated by the collision of a proton beam with a production target, which results in a shower of pions that will then decay into muons. These muons are generated with a large angular spread and a large momentum spread. The capture and cooling section will maximize the number of particles captured, and reduce their transverse momentum through interactions with an array of cooling cells. A cooling cell is composed of a low-Z material absorber, which will reduce both the longitudinal and the transverse momentum with minimal particle loss, a Radio-Frequency (RF) cavity that will re-accelerate the particles to restore their longitudinal momentum, and solenoids, that help focusing the beam and maintain the right (small) value of the beta function at the absorber position. Going through the sequence of cells as described in

Table 4: Main parameters for the rectilinear cooling cell components, including the cell geometry, solenoid fields, dipole fields, beam optics and wedge absorber geometry. Liquid hydrogen is used as the wedge absorber material for all stages., the beam is cooled, meaning the particles decrease their

transverse energy and their energy spread. The cooling performance is critical for the luminosity of the collider. A pre-conceptual design of cooling cells for rectilinear and final cooling had been developed before 2016 by the US-MAP. The goal of WP8 is to provide a complete mechanical design of one chosen type of cell to understand the issues of integration of the three main components and prove that the assumptions of the design are correct (see Fig. 35).

The section is organized like this: first we discuss in section 3.9.1 the advance in the design of the RFMFTF ((Radio Frequency in Magnetic Field Test Facility), that beside to be a key RF test stand is also the first demonstration of a split coil in HTS with characteristics similar to the ones of the real 6D cooling cell. The magnet and cryostat design developed for the RFMFTF split coil is then used for the first integration exercise on the 6D rectilinear cooling cell that is discussed in section 3.9.2.

Fig. 35: schematic design of the cell being integrated by WP8

3.9.1. Progress in the design and integration of the Split Coil for the RFMFTF

As a preliminary objective of the R&D phase toward a Muon Collider, the IMCC collaboration [26] has proposed the construction of a test facility for RF cavities in high magnetic fields, as mentioned in the RF section, see 3.6, under the name of RF test stand. The proposed facility, that here we will call *Radio Frequency in Magnetic Field Test Facility* (RFMFTF), aims both at testing the RF cavity breakdown limits under high magnetic fields (7 T) in a configuration relevant to the Muon Collider, and at being the first HTS split coil with characteristics similar to the HTS coils of the 6D rectilinear cooling cells. Therefore, the magnetic system of the RFMFTF serves to the integration of the cell for determining, in a relatively simple system, the actual size of the structure around the HTS coil and the space needed for cryostat and vacuum envelope. These are key information for the integration design of the cooling cell. In addition, the construction of this test facility will provide a

significant step toward defining a baseline technology for the 6D cooling cells of the Muon Collider, serving as a proof of concept for the cooling cell design [33] [34].

A layout has been proposed and studied by the LASA laboratory (University of Milan and INFN-Milan), which is currently finalizing the design before proceeding with construction, commissioning, and testing, if the project will be financed.

The RFMFTF test facility consists of a split coil made of HTS operated at 20 K for energy efficiency. The coils are of the non-insulated type, with a relatively high interturn resistance to limit heating during current ramp-up. The results of the conceptual design of the test facility, along with its layout and main parameters, have been presented in [35] [36]. The selected bore aperture of the split-coil magnets is suitable for testing RF cavities with frequencies of 1.3 GHz, or higher. Other options with a reduced bore aperture are currently under consideration for testing only 3 GHz (or higher frequency) cavities.

Fig. 36: Schematic view of the test facility with cryostat (a). Section view of the coil stack with steel casing (b).

The core structure of the test facility consists of a large-bore split coil based on HTS conductors (Fig. 31 a). Each of the two cylindrical coils features a winding made of 12 mm × 0.067 mm REBCO tape and 12 mm × 0.026 mm stainless steel tape, following an approach similar to that described in [37].

The facility is designed to operate both in with the same current polarity in two coils (“++” configuration) and with opposite polarity (“+-” configuration), each meeting specific field requirements [36], as summarized in Table I. It operates at 20 K in a cryogen-free configuration, by means of SHI SRDK-500B2 cryocoolers, chosen for their cooling capacity at the target operational temperature [38].

Structural support and thermal management for the coils are provided by an AISI 304L steel vacuum vessel. The cold heads are integrated into the support structure and connected to the coils at 20 K via aluminum thermal bridges (Fig. 36a). A 60 K thermal shield is incorporated, along with HTS current leads and copper busbars. The entire structure is mounted on a ground support platform, with three-point gravity supports ensuring optimal alignment. This approach could also be a viable option for the support system of the 6D cooling cells.

The coil structure, shown in Fig. 36b, was first proposed in [39]. It consists of a stack of six pancakes, each with 490 turns, enclosed within two coaxial copper rings and interleaved with layers of copper, stainless steel, and G-10 insulating material (Fig. 36b). The copper rings are soldered onto the innermost and outermost conductor turns of each pancake to ensure electrical connectivity. Copper layers serve as cooling elements, being thermally linked to the cryocoolers’ cold heads, while

the steel/G-10 layers function as support plates and provide insulation between pancakes. Table 11 summarizes the main geometric and operational parameters [36].

Table 11: List of main parameters from preliminary design

Parameter	Value
Coil bore diameter (free bore) [mm]	400(320)
Number of pancakes per coil (turns per pancake) [-]	6 (490)
Coil radial width (axial) [mm]	45.6 (107)
Coil winding method	Metal Insulated
Coils distance [mm]	200
Center field on axis (++) [T]	7
Field gradient on axis (+-) [T/m]	40
Coil total inductance [H]	4.54
Energy stored in the coil [MJ]	6.4
Coil operational temperature [K]	20
Thermal shield temperature [K]	60
Cooling strategy	Cryocoolers

A full finite element method (FEM) model of the charging transient of the split-coil magnets has been developed, with results presented in [40]. This approach enables the simulation of complex transient effects in non-insulated coils, ensuring the required axial and radial current fidelity. The electromagnetic (EM) model has been coupled with thermal and mechanical models to provide a comprehensive multiphysics representation of the coil charging transient.

To reduce the charging time, a metal-insulation winding has been considered, **decreasing it to less than three hours**—compared to the 20 hours estimated in the conceptual design, which assumed a fully non-insulated coil. The field and current evolution during the charging transient is shown in Fig. 37a, while Fig. 37b presents the current density distribution normalized to the local J_c for a single coil stack. At the end of the transient, the minimum local current margin is 23.9%, comfortably above the target limit.

Fig. 37: “++” configuration. Field and current evolution during transient (a). J_c fraction at the end of transient (b).

A coupled transient thermal model has been developed to analyze the coil temperature evolution during charging and optimize the cooling strategy. The cooling system consists of two single-stage cryocoolers (50 W at 20 K capacity [38]) thermally linked to the coils via aluminum thermal connections and integrated copper fins and plates. The temperature distribution at the end of the current ramp (for the ++ configuration, the most demanding one) is such that the coils reach an average temperature of $T_{ave} \approx 24$ K, with a temperature uniformity of $\Delta T \approx 1$ K.

Given that the selected cryocooler has a minimum operational temperature of 15 K [38], it is feasible to operate it around 18 K with a moderate cooling capacity of approximately 40 W, allowing the coil operational temperature to be further reduced to the 20 K design target. Table II summarizes the main thermal design parameters, including the estimated static loads on the coils, peak power deposition during charging, and the cooldown time from 77 K to 20 K, evaluated using an analytical model.

The evaluation of the coil charging transient, one of the most demanding operational scenarios, did not reveal any critical issues. However, more conservative operational approaches could be adopted to prevent excessive coil overheating. For example, increasing the charging time from the minimum calculated value of three hours to six hours could further reduce power extraction from the cryocoolers. This adjustment is estimated to lower the peak coil temperature to a maximum of 25 K, providing a greater temperature margin for safer operation.

Table 12: List of the main thermal design parameters.

Parameter	Value
Number of cryocoolers [-]	2
Radiation power on the thermal shield (on the coil from shield) [W]	32.6 (0.1)
Conduction power on the coil [W]	10
Peak power deposited on both coils at charging (inverse polarity) [W]	81.9 (74.8)
Maximum temperature increase (inverse polarity) [K]	12.7 (11.6)
Total charging time [h]	~ 3
Coil cooldown time: 77K-20K [h]	11

3.9.2. First Integration exercise of the S5 Cooling Cell for the demonstrator

The IMCC collaboration has recently initiated a Muon Cooling Demonstrator program. The cooling cells are complex mechanical assemblies consisting of high-field, large-radius superconducting solenoids, absorbers, and high-gradient RF cavities, all tightly integrated. Among the different types of cooling cells, the S5-type has been selected as the candidate demonstrator cell, with its first conceptual design presented in May 2024 in the MuCol Deliverable Report D8.1 [35], highlighting the results of preliminary analyses studying the beam phase space parameters.

In the initial design phase, an ideal solenoid field based on the sum of harmonic components and a perfectly vertical dipole field was used to simulate the beam lattice. To proceed with the cell design, engineering analyses of the magnets and evaluations of system integration were necessary. The first demonstrator cell layout was derived from the preliminary design in [35]. However, the ideal solenoid specified there was lately deemed unfeasible due to high peak stresses on the coil and excessive axial force (approaching 190 MN). Additionally, modifications were needed to provide sufficient space for the vacuum vessel and mechanical structure integration.

Given the challenges in magnet design—such as the limited space available and the calculated minimum bore radius of 550 mm, which implied high stresses on the coils due to the high peak fields and currents needed to deliver a 9 T peak field on the beam axis—a novel approach was required. An algorithm was implemented in MATLAB/FEMM to scan coil geometrical parameters to find the optimal configuration capable of generating the target field at the beam axis. To reduce peak field and stress, the coil section was divided into two coils, each independently tuned in the coil scan algorithm.

Fig. 38: Magnetic flux density distribution (a), hoop stress distribution (b) in lattice conditions.

The resulting configuration, termed the "S5-demo 28.9T peak" solution, achieved a nearly 29T peak field on the coil section., see Fig. 33. This configuration was further studied using electromagnetic and mechanical models to evaluate feasibility under two operational modes: stand-alone cell operation and magnetic lattice periodicity (i.e., the presence of subsequent cell magnets with alternating fields). Stand-alone operation was the most critical, as it lacked the screening fields from adjacent cells operated with opposite polarity.

Though it is not the standard operational mode, it is worthwhile to note that a cell must be safe also in standalone operations, for three reasons:

1. Each individual cell needs to be tested singularly (like the LHC magnets) to be validated before to be assembled in the accelerator;

2. Even in the final cooling cell array, some cells has to be the start and then end of the subsection of the cooling cell. This start/end cooling cells do not have on one side the balancing forces given by symmetric adjacent cells (like the regular lattice cells). Therefore the start and end cells are operating in a way similar to the standalone cell.
3. In case of a quench, one may lose totally or partially the field of a coil or of a cell: in this case a situation partially similar to a standalone.

The mechanical analysis of the "S5-demo 28.9T peak" solution showed that peak hoop stresses on the coils exceeded 1000 MPa, far surpassing material limits, while net axial forces on the coils reached 71 MN in lattice conditions, posing significant challenges for mechanical support structure design.

To proceed further with near-to-realistic parameters, we reduced arbitrarily the current density by 25% in the same coil configuration. Although this reduced the peak field on the beam axis to 6.5 T (failing to meet beam optics requirements), we used it for a preliminary cell integration exercise, to understand problems and work out issues also to give guidelines to magnet designers on practical and realistic space to be allocated and geometrical envelopes. An extract of the CAD drawings of the first cell layout is reported in Fig. 39, as presented at the Fermilab Workshop in October 2024 [1].

Fig. 39: Schematic view of the first layout of the S5-like demo cell, with solenoid mechanical (no dipole) and the 3 cell-RF cavity with its power feeding line. Left: 3D view. Right: cross section with dimension in mm.

The coil support structure was designed to withstand axial forces in both lattice and stand-alone configurations. The axial forces were calculated as +50 MN towards the cell center and -20 MN in the outer cell direction. Mechanical analysis determined that eight 200 mm diameter INCONEL 718 rods were required to support the coils in lattice conditions. However, heat dissipation in the tie rods posed a significant challenge: estimated power extraction was approximately 1.5 kW, making this solution thermally and economically unfeasible. As a result, a revised layout was needed.

An updated demonstrator cell layout was proposed following iterations with beam physicists and RF experts. A reduction in coil radii was necessary, increasing the space available for the coils inside the cell. In the revised layout, the cell length was increased from 0.8 m to 1 m – without increasing

the number of cavity, therefore decreasing the so-called “real estate gradient”- and the external absorber flange diameter was reduced from 300 mm to 260 mm. This significantly increased the space available for the coils and allowed for the integration of a small correction coil at a 185 mm radius.

In addition, as presented in the Fermilab workshop, to limit the heavy input we had to abandon the initial baseline solution of single cryostat for each coil side, i.e. two cryostats for one cell, as shown in Fig. 39. In the Fermilab workshop of 2024 it was proposed to go to the solution termed as "inter-cell cryostat" layout, displayed in Fig. 40, showing an array of three cells.

Fig. 40: Schematic view of the new cell layout based on the **inter-cell cryostat** concept. Violet envelope shows the intercell cryostat, while the yellow envelope shows the “optical lattice” cooling cell.

This new Inter-Cell Cryostat layout integrates the magnet support structure of two adjacent cells within a single cryostat, i.e. it enclose in the same cold envelope the right side coil of the (n-1)-th cell with the left side coil of the n-th cell, violet envelope in Fig. 40, then there is a room temperature separation to allocate the power coupler of the RF cavity, as well as other functions like vacuum pumping lines, instrumentation, etc.; then the next cryostat includes the right-side coil of the n-th cell and the left side coil of the (n+1)-th cell. This solution enhances mechanical stability, simplifies assembly and integration, and reduces cryogenic load. The increase in cell length to 1 m reduces the peak field on the beam axis to 7 T (from the original 9 T peak), with strong benefits for the magnet design.

An intermediate coil layout, referred to as the "17 MN 10 mm gap" option, was selected as a baseline design between November and December 2024. This configuration maintained axial alignment of the coil ends and enabled an initial integration exercise for the inter-cell layout. However, further coil optimizations were subsequently found.

For the magnet design, a new set of geometrical constraints was defined, and the coil search algorithm was updated and intensively used. To conduct an engineering analysis of the optimized coil configurations, details of the winding and assembly were considered. The proposed coil winding was derived from the ESMA magnet [37] and consisted of two 12 mm × 0.0656 mm FFJ HTS tapes [41] co-wound with a 12 mm × 0.026 mm stainless steel tape. The stainless steel tape increased contact resistance between turns (reducing coil time constants) and improved mechanical design by

increasing radial stiffness. Inter-pancake stainless steel spacers (4 mm thick in "Coil 1" and 3 mm in "Coil 2") were included for axial support, limiting stress accumulation. Fig. 41 shows the discretized coil sections and the selected winding scheme.

Fig. 41: Schematic view of the discretized coil sections (a). Winding scheme adopted, derived by ESMA (b)

The optimized configuration, termed the "12 MN 40 mm gap" option, was identified as the best balance between operational requirements and mechanical feasibility. Fig. 42 displays the hoop, radial, and axial stresses on the coil sections in the selected configuration.

Fig. 42: Coil hoop (a) and radial (b) distributions. Von Mises stress on the SS spacers (c) of the coil solution "12 MN 40 mm gap" that is currently used for integration studies.

This solution features, among other advantages, improved performance, with net axial forces reduced to 12 MN (compared to 50 MN in the previous design). The mechanical analysis of the coil support structure confirmed feasibility, with peak Von Mises stress reaching 418 MPa in the innermost corner of the 'Coil 2' housing—well within the mechanical limits of AISI 316 LN at 20 K (Fig. 43).

Fig. 43: Von Mises Stress distribution (a) and total deformation (b) of 1/8 section of coil support structure.

In conclusion this second year of MuCol study, has seen a bolt step-through in the integration of the cooling cell, with the new concept [42] of Inter-Cell Cryostat layout that seems the most favorable solution. A study of the assembly procedure is under way and at least one feasible solution was found, while the study of the cooling cell array (stage) start and termination, possible a weak point of the Inter-Cell Cryostat layout, will be carried in a second phase.

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ANNEX

ANNEX 1 : LIST OF MUCOL PAPERS

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